

Adaptive Enemy Behavior through Reinforcement Learning in an Action Role-Playing Game

Karim Sid Ahmed

*Master's Degree Program Artificial Intelligence Engineering
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
karim.vwa@gmail.com*

Julian Breddy

*Software Engineering & Architecture
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
julian.breddy@technikum-wien.at*

Jürgen Konrad, MSc

*Software Engineering & Architecture
University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien
Vienna, Austria
juergen.konrad@technikum-wien.at*

Abstract—Elevating enemy behavior to sustain player engagement while preserving a fair challenge is a fundamental requirement in modern action games. Advances in artificial intelligence, and reinforcement learning (RL) in particular, open new ways to model unique and adaptive combatants compared with traditional rule-based tools such as behavior trees (BT). This paper evaluates an RL-driven enemy with adaptive behavior against a traditional BT-driven enemy in the action role-playing game (RPG) *Shattered Bonds*, built in Unreal Engine 5. A hybrid agent was implemented in which a Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) policy makes high-level tactical decisions while a behavior tree handles operational tasks such as movement and orientation. A mixed-method user study with 44 participants was conducted, in which each participant faced both enemies in a randomized order, rated the encounters on a five-point Likert scale, and was logged through a custom telemetry system. The results indicate a consistent directional trend toward higher engagement for the RL agent while difficulty and fairness remained adequate. Subjective ratings differed significantly in difficulty ($p = 0.0011$), predictability ($p = 0.0056$), tactical waiting ($p = 0.0390$), strategy ($p = 0.0008$), and playstyle adaptation ($p = 0.0184$), whereas perceived fairness did not differ ($p = 0.9286$). Telemetry showed that encounters against the RL agent were significantly longer (mean 312.84 s vs. 256.80 s, $p = 0.0414$) and more lethal (mean 2.86 vs. 1.95 player deaths, $p = 0.0047$). A majority of participants preferred the RL agent as more human-like (63.6%, $\chi^2 p < 0.0001$) and more entertaining (65.9%, $\chi^2 p < 0.0001$), making it the preferred opponent. While the study confirms distinct benefits of RL for video-game enemies, it also concludes that the full potential of RL in complex combat environments has not yet been reached.

Index Terms—adaptive enemy behavior, reinforcement learning, behavior trees, player engagement, enemy AI, action role-playing games

I. INTRODUCTION

Engaging and challenging gameplay has become a key success factor in commercial games [1], [2], and enemy design is central to that experience. Well-designed enemy AI can raise difficulty and improve the overall experience through strategic placement and complex decision-making [3]. A useful the-

oretical anchor for this experience is the concept of *flow*: an optimal state achieved when player ability and challenge are in balance, allowing the player to engage intensely and experience satisfaction rather than stress or boredom [4].

With established AI tools such as behavior trees and state trees, developers can build enemies that initially pose a meaningful threat. However, these systems rely heavily on rule-based and hard-coded patterns. Such patterns can be learned and exploited by players, leading to reduced engagement once weaknesses are discovered [5]. Behavior trees also scale poorly: adding conditions reduces observability and complicates maintenance, and minor changes can alter the entire decision logic and make balancing difficult.

Reinforcement learning (RL) offers a way to overcome these limitations. Rather than relying on hand-crafted logic, an agent learns a strategy through long-term reward optimization [6], removing the need to anticipate every possible player interaction and generalizing across the environment through neural networks. RL also enables a different difficulty-scaling methodology: whereas traditional RPGs typically increase enemy stats or levels, RL can sustain a challenging encounter through adaptive strategy rather than stat inflation.

This work investigates the following research question: *What measurable influence does a reinforcement-learning-based enemy AI have on combat behavior, player experience, and perceived fairness compared with a traditional behavior-tree-based AI in an action RPG environment?* To answer it, a new enemy archetype was prototyped with a diverse ability set and gameplay effects; a PPO-based agent was trained for high-level decision-making; and a rule-based behavior tree served as the baseline. Player experience was evaluated through a questionnaire, and combat behavior was captured through a custom C++ logging system. The expected outcome was that greater adaptivity and unpredictability would increase engagement relative to the deterministic constraints of a static, rule-based behavior tree.

The study was conducted within *Shattered Bonds*, an action-adventure RPG developed in Unreal Engine 5 in which the player combines melee combat with the coordinated abilities of a party of companions. The present contribution focuses specifically on advancing the enemy design by transforming a previously script-driven adversary into an adaptive, RL-driven one.

II. METHODS

The objective was to develop a high-dimensional RL-based enemy agent and compare its behavior and player perception against a traditional, rule-based behavior-tree baseline. The following sections detail the technical framework, the architectural implementation, the training protocol, and the evaluation strategy.

A. Learning Framework

The agent was developed with the Learning Agents plugin for Unreal Engine, a native framework for training characters via reinforcement and imitation learning that communicates directly with the game’s actor logic [7]. The plugin was selected for three reasons: (i) *native integration*, with inter-actor communication handled within the engine’s memory space, reducing the latency typical of external approaches; (ii) *API accessibility* through C++ and Blueprints, accelerating prototyping and enabling deep integration with the Gameplay Ability System; and (iii) *visual debugging and logging*, allowing observations, actions, and rewards to be inspected after training runs to refine the agent’s strategy iteratively.

Reinforcement learning was selected over imitation learning. Although imitation learning behaves similarly and often trains faster, it relies on recordings of demonstrated behavior and was deemed insufficient for the goals of this work, which targeted emergent rather than mimicked strategy [8].

B. Agent Architecture

The Learning Agents framework organizes training around three components: a manager, an interactor, and an environment.

Manager. The manager registers the enemy as an agent and initializes the policy architecture (encoder, policy, decoder, and critic networks, stored as data assets). It also handles communication between the Unreal process and the Python training process through a shared-memory communicator, configures the PPO trainer, and holds the training hyperparameters and network settings. A single manager instance is placed in the scene to register all agents and run setup.

Interactor. The interactor is the interface between the policy and the game world, defining the observation and action spaces. The observation space is structured as key-value pairs: the self/enemy key contains location, rotation, health, current stance, offensive and defensive buff stacks, and cooldown timers for all eight abilities; the player key contains location, rotation, health, stamina, and active stance. Every floating-point observation is normalized to reduce complexity and improve network updates. The action space comprises

two decisions: *CombatChoice*, an exclusive-union action that first selects a stance (Offense, Defense, Buffs, or Idle) and then an ability within that stance; and *PowerUp*, a Boolean action determining whether the chosen ability is empowered. Structuring the action space as an exclusive union accelerates convergence by preventing the agent from having to learn which abilities belong to which stance, and it simplifies later integration with the behavior tree.

Environment. The environment implements the Markov decision process through three functions. The reward function uses seven weighted terms (covering attacking, defending, ultimate usage, buff stacking, and cooldown management); the agent is rewarded for damaging the player, maintaining its own health, stacking buffs, and using its ultimate successfully, with per-ability conditions governing reward or penalty. The completion function marks each episode as running, truncated, or terminated, terminating when either combatant is defeated. The reset function restores the positions, health, and AI logic of both combatants to enable continuous training.

C. Policy Optimization and Hybrid Control

Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) was selected for the agent’s decision-making. PPO is comparatively easy to tune and stable, mitigates destabilizing large policy updates, and reduces catastrophic forgetting, which makes it a robust choice for complex combat [9], [10]. It is also natively implemented in the Learning Agents plugin (Unreal Engine 5.5), which reduced development time. The training hyperparameters and network architecture are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
KEY TRAINING HYPERPARAMETERS AND NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

Setting	Value
Algorithm	PPO
Learning rate (policy)	0.0002
Learning rate (critic)	0.0005
Policy batch size	1024
Critic batch size	4096
Policy window size	128
Action entropy weight	0.01
Epsilon clip	0.2
GAE λ	0.95
Discount factor	0.99
Policy network	3 hidden layers, 256 units, ELU
Critic network	3 hidden layers, 256 units, ELU
Memory state size	128

The enemy used the Gameplay Ability System as its foundation, consistent with other enemies in the game. A hybrid architecture was implemented: the RL policy made high-level strategic decisions, while a behavior tree handled operational tasks such as movement and facing the player, executed prior to any action when required. This division offered three advantages: it improved *efficiency*, since learning basic navigation with RL is slow and hinders convergence; it *reduced unnecessary complexity*, preventing the agent from over-optimizing movement at the expense of tactical ability usage; and it preserved *extensibility*, allowing simple tasks

outside the scope of RL to be added as behavior-tree nodes. An interface function, `PerformCombatChoice`, received the policy’s actions and set the corresponding behavior-tree variables.

D. Abilities and Effects

The enemy featured a stance-categorized skill set in which abilities could be empowered by active status effects. Offensive abilities included a five-hit melee combo, a ground slam dealing area-of-effect damage, a sword throw projectile, and an offense ultimate that required three offense-buff stacks. Defensive abilities included blocking, a dodge counterstrike, a cooldown-free dodge, and a defense ultimate that consumed a buff stack to restore health. Offensive and defensive buffs acted as an empowerment mechanic, forcing the agent to learn the value of stacking buffs before committing to major attacks.

E. Comparative Configurations

Two AI configurations were developed. The *RL-driven* configuration used a deliberately simple tree with branches for offense, defense, buffs, idle, and passive behavior, plus a high-priority `BTT_Thinking` task that ran the trained policy and selected the action for each decision cycle. The *rule-based baseline* added explicit conditions, services that monitored attributes such as health, and per-node cooldown conditions; abilities were ordered by priority because behavior trees evaluate nodes left to right [11]. To mirror the RL agent’s empowerment mechanic, the baseline chose randomly whether the next ability would be empowered. Balancing the baseline tree became exponentially more difficult as the number of abilities grew, illustrating a key limitation of scripted systems and leading to unwanted behavior and lengthy development.

F. Training Protocol

Training was conducted in a dedicated level containing 20 enemy agents and 20 player AIs, each pair placed in a separate arena with two reset points. The hardware was a single NVIDIA RTX 3070 (8 GB VRAM). Sessions ranged from 2 to 10 hours depending on the reward function under test, and the final run lasted 14 continuous hours. Each run was logged to TensorBoard for evaluation of average reward, episode length, and policy stability.

G. Evaluation Methodology

A mixed-method design combined qualitative questionnaire feedback with quantitative telemetry. Each participant faced both enemies in a randomized order to reduce ordering bias, yielding two experimental groups: Group A encountered the RL agent first, and Group B encountered the behavior-tree enemy first. Data were recorded continuously in the background, and participants provided subjective feedback after each encounter.

The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale, chosen for its balance between informativeness and respondent burden [12], and was organized around perceived fairness, unpredictability and adaptivity, and engagement and flow.

Several general items, such as difficulty, were inspired by the Game Experience Questionnaire (GEQ) [13]; however, a more granular, context-specific instrument was required because standardized frameworks lack the sensitivity to measure specialized combat mechanics such as strategic stance switching. The telemetry system logged combat duration (time from encounter start until the enemy was defeated or the encounter was skipped), player deaths (respawn events), and an encounter-skip flag (available only after two consecutive defeats). Telemetry was logged silently to avoid placing pressure on participants, and the two data streams were later compared to identify correlations.

For statistical analysis, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied to the ordinal Likert items, since a normal distribution cannot be assumed for paired ordinal data [14], and the chi-square goodness-of-fit test was applied to the categorical preference items to assess deviation from a uniform distribution [15]. Significance was assessed at the 0.05 threshold. In the context of the research question, the notion of *measurable influence* was operationalized by translating subjective player experience into quantifiable outcomes: although the questionnaire captured perceptions, the responses were subjected to significance testing and triangulated against the objective telemetry metrics, allowing qualitative impressions to be expressed as measurable, statistically grounded differences between the two configurations.

III. RESULTS

A total of 44 participants took part in the study. The questionnaire, administered through an online form, comprised an introduction and basic items, a block of identical questions for each enemy (administered after the respective encounter), and a final block of direct comparison items with an optional free-text comment field.

A. Training Convergence and Validation

The final 14-hour training run showed clear evidence of convergence (Fig. 1). Average episode length began high, reflecting an early exploration phase with no consistent strategy, and then declined markedly around the 1,500-step mark, indicating that the agent had learned to defeat the player AI more efficiently. Average reward improved rapidly before stabilizing roughly halfway through the run, and cumulative reward per episode rose to approximately 40,000–45,000 units with no signs of systemic policy degradation or catastrophic forgetting. The critic network’s loss remained low relative to the reward magnitude, indicating accurate value prediction [16]. Training was stopped after 14 hours because further training yielded no significant performance gains and tended to distort the policy toward extreme, state-decoupled behavior.

B. Participant Demographics

The sample concentrated in young-adult demographics: the 25–34 bracket accounted for roughly half of participants, followed by the 18–25 bracket, consistent with the typical commercial-gaming audience [17]. Of the participants, 65.8%

Fig. 1. Training convergence of the RL agent over the final run. Top left: average episode length, which declines as the agent learns to defeat the player AI more efficiently. Top right: average reward per step, which rises rapidly and then plateaus. Bottom left: cumulative average reward per episode, stabilizing around 40,000–45,000 units. Bottom right: critic-network loss, which decreases and stabilizes, indicating increasingly accurate value prediction. Raw values are shown in light orange and the smoothed trend in solid orange.

reported occasional to highly frequent engagement with action RPGs, while the remainder were comparatively genre-naïve, helping to ensure the evaluation was not biased toward genre veterans. Self-reported combat skill was negatively skewed toward higher tiers (average to expert), and prior experience with machine-learning or adaptive game AI was balanced across the sample, reducing potential bias from prior exposure to adaptive enemies.

C. Player Experience

Subjective ratings were evaluated across five experiential areas, each comprising multiple Likert items, followed by direct preference comparisons. The results consistently favored the RL agent.

Difficulty and fairness. Difficulty and fairness are closely coupled in enemy design, and balancing them is essential to producing interesting encounters while avoiding player frustration [18]. The RL agent was rated consistently more difficult (median 4, interquartile range [IQR] 3.8–5) than the behavior-tree baseline (median 2, IQR 2–3), which was generally rated easy to moderate (Fig. 2). The high concentration of responses

at scores 4 and 5 indicates that the learned strategy applied sustained pressure on players. Perceived fairness was comparable for both enemies (median 3.0, IQR 1) and clustered around the centre of the scale, indicating that the higher difficulty of the RL agent was not perceived as artificial.

Predictability. Predictability strongly affects an encounter: an enemy that is too easy to read becomes monotonous, while one that is entirely unpredictable can become frustrating. The behavior-tree enemy was perceived as substantially more predictable (median 4, IQR 3–5), whereas the RL agent achieved a lower predictability (median 2), with most responses concentrated around scores 2 and 3. This confirms that the trained policy varied its executed actions enough to resist being easily read without descending into incoherence.

Reactivity and stance logic. The RL agent received a higher reactivity rating (median 4) than the baseline (median 2). For stance-switching logic, both enemies shared a similar spread (IQR 2–4), but central tendencies favored the RL agent.

Decision-making. The RL agent was rated higher for tactical patience (median 4 vs. 2) and for strategic intent (median 4 vs. 2), and players reported that it forced greater playstyle

Fig. 2. Perceived-difficulty ratings (five-point Likert) for the RL (adaptive) and BT (classic) configurations across the full sample ($N = 44$). The RL agent concentrates at the upper scores (median 4, IQR 3.8–5), whereas the baseline is rated easy to moderate (median 2, IQR 2–3); the difference is statistically significant (Wilcoxon signed-rank, $p = 0.0011$).

adaptation (median 3 vs. 2; Fig. 3). Reaction time, by contrast, showed near-perfect overlap (both median 3), indicating that players perceived no difference in execution or response speed.

Fig. 3. Perceived playstyle-adaptation ratings (five-point Likert) for the RL (adaptive) and BT (classic) configurations across the full sample ($N = 44$). Players reported that the RL agent forced greater adaptation of their own playstyle (median 3 vs. 2), whereas the baseline did not; the difference is statistically significant (Wilcoxon signed-rank, $p = 0.0184$).

Order effects. Comparing the two groups revealed consistent contrast effects driven by encounter order: participants who faced the rigid behavior-tree baseline first (Group B)

reported a pronounced upward shift when switching to the RL agent—most strongly for decision-making and stance logic—whereas the RL agent’s own ratings remained comparatively stable across both groups. This confirms that counterbalancing the encounter order was warranted and that initial exposure to the baseline accentuated the perceived adaptivity of the RL agent; a full per-group breakdown is provided in the underlying thesis.

A consolidated profile across all metrics is shown in Fig. 4, and per-category significance is reported in Table II. The differences were statistically significant for difficulty, predictability, tactical waiting, strategy, and playstyle adaptation, but not for fairness, stance logic, or reaction time. The non-significant fairness and reaction-time results are themselves informative: they indicate that the RL agent did not default to frame-perfect execution or mechanical exploitation but instead learned a comparatively natural attack pattern.

TABLE II
PER-CATEGORY SIGNIFICANCE (WILCOXON SIGNED-RANK TEST)

Category	p -value
Difficulty	0.0011
Fairness	0.9286
Predictability	0.0056
Stance logic	0.3281
Tactical waiting	0.0390
Strategy	0.0008
Playstyle adaptation	0.0184
Reaction time	0.3958

D. Preference and Direct Comparison

In the direct comparison, a majority of participants selected the RL agent as more human-like in its decision-making (28 of 44, 63.6%) compared with the behavior-tree enemy (11, 25.0%), with 5 participants rating them equal (Fig. 5). Similarly, the RL agent was preferred for engagement and entertainment (29 of 44, 65.9%) over the baseline (12, 27.3%), with the remainder indicating no preference (Fig. 6). These preferences were stable across both experimental groups. The chi-square goodness-of-fit test confirmed that both preferences were highly significant: perceived humanity ($\chi^2 = 19.41$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.0001$) and entertainment preference ($\chi^2 = 23.77$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.0001$). The combined preference results are summarized in Fig. 7.

E. Telemetry

Three telemetry metrics were logged silently during every encounter: encounter duration, measured from the start of combat until the enemy was defeated or the encounter was skipped; player deaths, the number of respawn events; and an encounter-skip flag, which became available only after two consecutive defeats and recorded whether a participant chose to bypass an encounter. The telemetry data corroborated the subjective findings (Fig. 8, Table III). Encounters against the RL agent lasted longer (mean 312.84 s; median ≈ 270 s, IQR ≈ 160 –420 s, outliers reaching ≈ 870 s) than against the

Fig. 4. Subjective evaluation profiles across the two enemy configurations (mean Likert rating per metric), with significance assessed via a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$).

Fig. 5. Perceived-humanity preference: number of player votes for the RL (adaptive), BT (classic), and “both/neither” options across the full sample ($N = 44$).

Fig. 6. Entertainment preference: number of player votes for the RL (adaptive), BT (classic), and “both/neither” options across the full sample ($N = 44$).

behavior-tree baseline (mean 256.80 s; median < 200 s, IQR ≈ 130 – 350 s). Player deaths shared a median of two for both enemies, but the RL agent produced a wider upper tail, with outliers reaching ten deaths, whereas the baseline was capped at six. Both telemetry differences were statistically significant (encounter time $p = 0.0414$; player deaths $p = 0.0047$).

The questionnaire order effects were mirrored in the telemetry: the extreme upper-tail death counts against the RL agent occurred predominantly among participants who had faced the behavior-tree baseline first, suggesting that initial exposure to the simpler enemy shaped the strategies players carried into the adaptive encounter.

Although longer encounters and higher death rates can conventionally signal poor balancing or frustration, the preference results suggest otherwise: participants actively selected the RL

TABLE III
TELEMETRY SUMMARY AND SIGNIFICANCE

Metric	RL enemy	BT enemy
Mean combat time (s)	312.84	256.80
Mean player deaths	2.86	1.95
Time significance	$p = 0.0414$	
Death significance	$p = 0.0047$	

agent as their preferred opponent, indicating that the increased pressure was experienced as engaging rather than frustrating.

C: Forced-Choice Global Player Preferences (Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit Test)

Fig. 7. Forced-choice global player preferences for perceived humanity and entertainment between the two AI configurations, expressed as a percentage of total votes (chi-square goodness-of-fit test).

Fig. 8. Objective combat telemetry for the RL (adaptive) and BT (classic) configurations across the full sample ($N = 44$). Left: recorded real-time combat engagement (seconds). Right: distribution of total player deaths.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Main Findings

Taken together, the survey and telemetry data indicate that an RL-based enemy positively influences combat behavior, player experience, and fairness. The RL agent established a distinct combat dynamic, evidenced by a significantly longer mean encounter duration (312.84 s) and higher death rate, aligned with significant subjective differences in predictability ($p = 0.0056$), tactical waiting ($p = 0.0390$), and overall strategy ($p = 0.0008$). The significant difference in playstyle

adaptation ($p = 0.0184$) and the explicit majority preference (63.6%) for the RL agent as the more engaging opponent point to higher engagement and entertainment. Importantly, the non-significant differences in fairness ($p = 0.9286$) and reaction time ($p = 0.3958$) show that players perceived almost no difference on these dimensions despite the distinct underlying logic, confirming that the RL model did not resort to frame-perfect execution or mechanical exploitation but learned a natural pattern of attacks and ability usage. Reinforcement learning thus appears capable of raising enemy complexity without overwhelming the player.

B. Limitations

Several factors constrain the strength of these conclusions. The sample of 44 participants means the findings should be interpreted as directional rather than definitive; larger participant pools would help validate the observed trends. In addition, the hybrid architecture, although effective, left part of the RL potential unrealized: the agent could not cancel active abilities, which would have allowed it to reassess situational parameters such as distance and abort suboptimal actions. This was partially mitigated by a cooldown-free dodge and an idle strafing state used as fallback actions, a workaround that players rated favorably for tactical patience, but ability cancellation remains the technically superior approach.

C. Comparison with Previous Work

The findings align with prior studies applying RL to non-player characters. Work comparing RL-driven and hard-scripted aiming behavior directly contrasted two characters and reported that the RL-trained variant behaved in a markedly more human-like manner, yielding a more immersive and dynamic player experience [19]. Studies of NPC behavior using engine-native ML frameworks reached an analogous conclusion, finding that behavior became noticeably more intuitive and less predictable when driven by machine learning rather than scripted logic [20]. PPO-based agents in turn-based strategy contexts produced an enjoyable challenge without creating an unfair environment and demonstrated a clear advantage over classical AI techniques [21], and RL has likewise been applied successfully to learn complex behaviors in first-person shooter agents, showing the method to be suitable for autonomous combat agents [22]. The present study extends this body of work to a high-dimensional action-RPG combat setting in which the agent selects among a large set of stance-conditioned abilities, and complements the largely qualitative emphasis of earlier studies with paired statistical testing and objective telemetry.

D. Implications

Although evaluated in a moderate RPG setting, the approach generalizes to any genre involving adversarial game AI, given the capacity of RL to master diverse behavioral spaces, and it can add structural complexity without extensive hard-coding. A particularly valuable application is live-service games: as studios gather player behavior data, enemies can be periodically retrained to adjust their strategies, sustaining fresh and engaging content. The approach also reframes balancing, shifting designer effort from tuning numerical values such as damage and health toward shaping strategic capabilities, so that players are challenged by counter-strategies rather than artificial difficulty spikes. This in turn encourages developers to define authentic behavioral guidelines rather than rely on static scripted triggers.

E. Future Work

Future research could investigate enemies fully controlled by RL, including movement and group coordination alongside simultaneous offense and defense. Such a design would

require a broader action and observation space and a step-wise curriculum-learning methodology to mitigate the unstable training and catastrophic forgetting that arise when optimizing many behaviors at once [23]. A second direction is real-time, in-session training: in a multi-phase encounter, downtime between phases could be used to gather the player's actions and fine-tune a pretrained policy to the individual's playstyle, making subsequent phases more engaging while avoiding erratic behavior. Provided developers invest the time and expertise to configure a well-structured reward function, RL agents can demonstrably enhance the overall player experience.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Karim Sid Ahmed conducted the research as part of the master's thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master's thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Julian Breddy supervised the research process as primary supervisor on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication. Jürgen Konrad, MSc, acted as second supervisor and provided detailed feedback that was highly valuable to the development of the thesis.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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